

Designing Vibrotactile Flow to Feel Space

—A Research-through-Design Exploration—

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Abstract. This study examines whether humans can infer spatial structures using vibration patterns “flowing” across the skin (vibrotactile flow) alone. We designed a system that presents relative motion as vibrotactile flow. Using a research-through-design approach, we conducted an exploratory case study in a virtual crossroad environment. Analysis of a single participant’s actions, verbalizations, and interview suggested that the participant initiated and adjusted active exploratory behaviors based on changes in the vibrotactile stimuli, gradually constructing an understanding of walls, junctions, and open spaces. These observations suggest that spatial understanding may emerge through modality-transcending spatial inference and indicate new design directions for vibrotactile navigation systems.

Keywords: Vibration stimuli, Modality conversion, Optical flow, Apparent motion, Work-in-progress, Research-through-design.

1 Introduction

Numerous haptic and vibrotactile interfaces have been developed to support mobility for people with visual impairments by conveying obstacle distance or travel direction through tactile cues [1–8]. However, such information is insufficient, as understanding real environments also requires perceiving spatial structures such as walls, corridors, junctions, and open spaces, which cannot be represented by distance cues alone.

Inspired by optical flow [9], a visual phenomenon in which motion is perceived from changes in the visual field, this study explores *vibrotactile flow* (Fig. 1), where relative motion is presented as vibration patterns flowing across the skin. These vibration patterns are intended to be interpreted through active bodily movement. Adopting a research-through-design (RtD) [10] perspective, this work-in-progress (WiP) study explores whether spatial structures can be inferred from vibrotactile flow alone. Our goal

Figure 1. Concept of vibrotactile flow. Relative motion mapped onto the skin.

is to generate design and cognitive hypotheses through an exploratory case study using the system as a research instrument, rather than validating performance.

2 Research Question and Approach

Based on this goal, we formulate the following research questions (RQs). **RQ1**: Can people perceive spatial structures through vibrotactile flow generated during exploratory movements? **RQ2**: Which actions and exploratory strategies do people use to make spatial inferences under uncertainty?

These RQs focus on human perception and inference rather than system performance. Accordingly, we adopt an RtD approach, emphasizing in-depth observation of sensorimotor interaction over statistical generalization.

Therefore, we conduct a qualitative case study with a single participant to closely examine sensorimotor interaction. The observations are intended to provide hypothesis-generating evidence. The participant’s actions, verbalizations, and exploratory processes are analyzed to investigate how vibrotactile flow supports spatial inference and to generate hypotheses for future design.

3 Vibrotactile flow system

Our system maps user movement to vibrotactile stimuli to present spatial relationships as continuous flow (Fig. 2).

The vibrotactile stimuli are generated by three units positioned on the forehead. Each unit contains two vibration actuators and corresponds to a direction relative to the user’s heading. Apparent motion [11, 12] within each unit is produced by temporally offset vibrations between the actuators, representing the relative movement direction of objects in external space.

This design prioritizes relational motion cues over absolute distance encoding. The frontal placement was chosen to reflect the forward-oriented characteristics of optical flow during locomotion.

4 Exploratory Study

This study observes how perception and action are organized under uncertainty during embodied exploration.

We conducted an exploratory observational study with a single participant to examine whether spatial structures can be perceived through vibrotactile flow. This design enabled close observation of perception–action processes during exploratory

Figure 2. Vibrotactile unit configuration. Three forehead units generate apparent motion using temporally offset vibrations between paired actuators.

interaction and the generation of grounded hypotheses. The participant explored the environment without visual input while their movements were mapped onto a virtual environment that generated vibrotactile stimuli. Verbalizations and movement trajectories were recorded and followed by an interview.

As a representative observational example, during exploratory forward–backward movements in front of a wall, the overall intensity of the presented vibrotactile flow increased. The participant reported impressions such as “feeling as if touching a surface” and perceiving “planar information,” suggesting the perception of a surface based on vibration intensity and its symmetry. When the vibration intensity suddenly decreased, the participant reported that “the vibration disappeared” and that “the space opened up,” suggesting the perception of an opening in the surrounding space. These observations suggest that the participant integrated these cues into an understanding of spatial structures through active sensorimotor interaction.

5 Discussion and Generated Hypotheses

The findings suggest that spatial structures may be perceived through vibrotactile flow (**RQ1**), with spatial inference emerging through active exploratory actions such as movement and rotation under uncertainty (**RQ2**). These observations are consistent with the view that spatial understanding arises from an active perception–action cycle rather than from a specific sensory modality.

Based on these observations, we generate the following hypotheses to inform future validation and design. Concerning cognitive processes, we first hypothesize that vibrotactile flow does not function as a passively interpreted stimulus but rather operates as sensory information that gains meaning through active exploration coupled with action (**H1**) [13, 14]. We further hypothesize that, even without visual input, tactile information can support the perception of spatial structures (**H2**) [15–17]. That is, spatial inference may emerge through iterative cycles of prediction and verification grounded in sensorimotor interaction.

From a design perspective, we additionally hypothesize that, to support spatial cognition, vibration should be designed not as a distance or warning cue but as a flow representing relative motion (**H3**) [18–20]. That is, vibrotactile interfaces should support active exploration by presenting continuous relational information rather than discrete signals.

As a WiP study, these findings are offered as grounded hypotheses for future validation rather than as generalizable conclusions.

Future work will extend the system to omnidirectional presentation using a ring configuration and investigate a wider range of spatial environments.

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